

1 **A high-throughput phenotyping tool to identify field-relevant**
2 **anthracnose resistance in white lupin**

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16

17 **Abstract**

18 The seed- and air-borne pathogen *Colletotrichum lupini*, the causal agent of lupin anthracnose,
19 is the most important disease in white lupin (*Lupinus albus*) worldwide and can cause total yield
20 loss. The aims of this study were to establish a reliable high-throughput phenotyping tool to
21 identify anthracnose resistance in white lupin germplasm and to evaluate a genomic prediction
22 model, accounting previously reported resistance QTLs, on a set of independent lupin genotypes.
23 Phenotyping under controlled conditions, performing stem inoculation on seedlings, showed to
24 be applicable for high-throughput and its disease score strongly correlated with field plot disease
25 assessments ($r = 0.95$, $p < 0.0001$) and yield ($r = -0.64$, $p = 0.035$). Traditional 1-row field disease
26 phenotyping showed no significant correlation with field plot disease assessments ($r = 0.31$,
27 $p = 0.34$) and yield ($r = -0.45$, $p = 0.17$). Genomically-predicted resistance values showed no
28 correlation with values observed under controlled or field conditions, and the parental lines of
29 the RIL population used for constructing the prediction model exhibited a resistance pattern
30 opposite to that displayed in the original (Australian) environment used for model construction.
31 Differing environmental conditions, inoculation procedures or population structure may account
32 for this result. Phenotyping a diverse set of 40 white lupin accessions under controlled conditions
33 revealed eight accessions with improved resistance to anthracnose. The standardized area under
34 the disease progress curves (sAUDPC) ranged from 2.1 to 2.8 compared to the susceptible
35 reference accession with a sAUDPC of 3.85. These accessions can be incorporated into white lupin
36 breeding programs. In conclusion, our data supports stem inoculation-based disease
37 phenotyping under controlled conditions as a time-effective approach to identify field-relevant

38 resistance which can now be applied to further identify sources of resistance and their underlying
39 genetics.

40

41 **Keywords:** *Lupinus albus*, *Colletotrichum lupini*, wound inoculation, field resistance, breeding,

42 genomic prediction

43 The current demand for plant-based protein is high and is expected to increase even
44 further with the growing world population (Henchion et al. 2017). Most of the global demand is
45 met by soybean produced on a large-scale in the USA and Brazil (Pagano and Miransari 2016). As
46 lupins have a similar protein content and better digestibility (Monteiro et al. 2014), they offer
47 great potential to complement soybean as an alternative protein source (Lucas et al. 2015). The
48 genus *Lupinus*, belonging to the family *Fabaceae*, consists of about 170 species worldwide, with
49 blue (*Lupinus angustifolius* L.), Andean (*L. mutabilis*), yellow (*L. luteus* L.) and white lupin (*L. albus*
50 L.) being of agricultural importance (Gresta et al. 2017). Their unique symbiosis with
51 *Bradyrhizobium* sp. (*lupini*) makes lupins highly efficient atmospheric nitrogen fixers (Fernández-
52 Pascual et al. 2007; Peix et al. 2015). Additionally, white lupin is capable of forming specialized
53 cluster roots which release carboxylates to mobilize poorly available phosphorus sources
54 (Gallardo et al. 2019; Lambers et al. 2013). White lupin is recognized for its high protein content
55 (36 to 38%), starch-free white seeds, outstanding fatty acid quality and additional health benefits,
56 making its grains ideal for the food and feed industry (Arnoldi et al. 2015; Boschini et al. 2008;
57 Monteiro et al. 2014).

58 Despite its potential for low-input agriculture as highlighted above, the cultivation of
59 white lupin has been severely limited by anthracnose disease caused by the seed- and air-borne
60 ascomycete *Colletotrichum lupini*, which is a member of the *Colletotrichum acutatum* species
61 complex (Damm et al. 2012; Nirenberg et al. 2002). Contrary to the broad host range seen for
62 most members of the *C. acutatum* species complex, *C. lupini* is host-specific to members of the
63 *Lupinus* genus (Talhinhas et al. 2016). Infected seeds are the primary source of inoculum and
64 small amounts of infected seeds (0.1%) can cause severe yield loss (Thomas and Sweetingham

65 2004). Little is known about the disease cycle and interaction between *C. lupini* and its host but
66 gene expression and protein synthesis during white lupin infection shared similarities to those of
67 hemibiotrophic pathogens (Dubrulle et al. 2020a), which is the most common lifestyle within the
68 *C. acutatum* species complex (De Silva et al. 2017; Peres et al. 2005). At the start of the growing
69 season, *C. lupini* is believed to colonize the host endophytically, causing no to minor disease
70 symptoms. Upon flowering, disease incidence rapidly increases, causing the typical disease
71 symptoms of stem elongation and pod twisting, followed by the formation of necrotic lesions
72 containing orange masses of conidia which are rain-splash dispersed within the crop (Thomas
73 and Sweetingham 2004, White et al. 2008). At first, the disease occurred predominantly in humid
74 areas but it has quickly spread around the globe, making anthracnose the most notorious disease
75 for lupin cultivation worldwide (Talhinhas et al. 2016). The current disease epidemic in Europe
76 started in the 1970's, coinciding with a strong decline in lupin cultivated area (FAOSTAT 2017).
77 Currently, disease management of white lupin is focused on planting pathogen-free seed and
78 chemical control (Thomas et al. 2008a; White et al. 2008).

79 Breeding efforts for anthracnose resistance mainly took place under field conditions in
80 New Zealand, Australia, Chile and Germany (Adhikari et al. 2009; Cowling et al. 2000; Jacob et al.
81 2017; von Baer 2009). These efforts have led to the discovery of resistance in the Ethiopian
82 landraces P27174 and P27175 (Adhikari et al. 2009; Cowling et al. 2000), which form a distinct
83 genetic group within white lupin (Raman et al. 2014). Analysis of a recombinant inbred line (RIL)
84 population of P27174 and the susceptible cultivar Kiev Mutant revealed that the resistance was
85 under polygenic control (Yang et al. 2010), which is also the case for yellow lupin (Adhikari et al.
86 2011), and unlike blue lupin, where single dominant genes, *Lanr1*, *AnMan* or *LanrBo*, control

87 anthracnose resistance (Fischer et al. 2015; Yang et al. 2004; Yang et al. 2008). Quantitative trait
88 locus (QTL) mapping of the RIL population between P27174 and Kiev Mutant revealed three
89 major anthracnose resistance QTLs, antr04/05_1, antr04/05_2 and antr05_3, on linkage groups
90 ALB02 (LG4), ALB04 (LG17) and ALB10 (LG2), respectively, and jointly explained up to 49% of the
91 phenotyping variation observed under field conditions in 2004 and 2005 in Western Australia
92 (Phan et al. 2007; Yang et al. 2010). The same QTLs, were recently identified with greater
93 precision by Książkiewicz et al. (2017) using a large number of SNP markers identified from
94 genotyping-by-sequencing (GBS; Elshire et al. 2011). Despite the high synteny between blue and
95 white lupin, QTLs conferring anthracnose resistance in white lupin did not correspond to those
96 found in the latter species (Książkiewicz et al. 2017). The high number of markers made available
97 by GBS not only facilitated QTL mapping but also opened the way for genomic selection, by which
98 a statistical model is constructed from phenotypic and genotypic data of a representative
99 population to predict breeding values for a target (polygenic) trait of inbred lines or genetic
100 resources (Heffner et al. 2009). A genomic prediction model, proposed to aid in marker assisted
101 selection based on the RIL population used to identify the major QTLs, showed a predictive ability
102 of 0.56 for anthracnose resistance and also took into account variation not explained by the
103 observed QTLs (Rychel-Bielska et al. 2020).

104 Disease phenotyping under field conditions is subject to unpredictable environmental
105 conditions. Therefore, reliable screening tools for anthracnose resistance are essential to further
106 exploit genetic diversity within white lupin. This study describes a reproducible and time-
107 effective phenotyping tool for anthracnose resistance breeding, performing stem inoculation on
108 seedlings under controlled conditions. For this, a diverse collection of white lupin landraces that

109 was shown to include outstanding material for key traits such as grain yield in different climatic
110 zones (Annicchiarico et al. 2010) and drought tolerance (Annicchiarico et al. 2018), which likely
111 holds new sources of anthracnose resistance, was used. The objectives of this study were to (i)
112 compare the developed high-throughput phenotyping tool and traditional 1-row field
113 assessments with field plot assessments obtained over two years at two sites, (ii) identify
114 anthracnose resistance in a collection of 40 white lupin accessions and (iii) evaluate the
115 consistency of resistance values predicted according to the Rychel-Bielska et al. (2020) genomic
116 prediction model with resistance values observed under controlled and field conditions for an
117 unrelated germplasm set.

118 **Materials and Methods**

119 ***Colletotrichum lupini* strain characterization.** *C. lupini* strain JA01, used as inoculum in
120 this study, was isolated from pod tissue of an infected white lupin plant in 2018 in Mellikon,
121 Switzerland (47°34'05.7"N 8°21'18.7"E). Mycelium from a pure JA01 culture, grown for 10 days
122 on PDA (potato dextrose agar, Carl Roth®, Karlsruhe, Germany) at 22°C in the dark, was harvested
123 with a sterile spreader after flooding the Petri dish with 2 ml sterile ddH₂O. Genomic DNA was
124 isolated with a CTAB extraction protocol as described by Minas et al. (2011). The 5.8S nuclear
125 ribosomal gene with the two flanking internal transcribed spacers (ITS) was amplified by
126 performing PCR in a S1000 Thermal Cycler (Bio-Rad, CA, USA) using the ITS5
127 “GGAAGTAAAAGTCGTAACAAG” and ITS4 “TCCTCCGCTTATTGATATGC” (White et al. 1990)
128 primers as described by Dubrulle et al. (2020b). PCR products were purified using the QIAquick®
129 PCR Purification Kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany) and sent for sequencing to Eurofins Genomics
130 (Ebersberg, Germany). The consensus sequence was assembled using BioEdit v. 7.2.5 (Hall 2004)
131 and identified as *C. lupini* through BLAST analysis and deposited at GenBank under accession
132 number MT741840. Australian *C. lupini* strain IMI 375715 (genetic group 2; Dubrulle et al. 2020b)
133 was used in one experiment to compare with strain JA01 for virulence on white lupin.

134 **Genomic prediction.** The genomic prediction model was based on results published by
135 Rychel-Bielska et al. (2020). The germplasm used for genomic prediction modelling included 191
136 F₈ individuals issued from the RIL population of Kiev Mutant x P27174. Phenotypic data was
137 collected in Perth (Western Australia) from two experiments in 2004 and 2005 (three replicates),
138 under field conditions in a 1-row setup, using spray-inoculated (*C. lupini* strain IMI 375715)
139 disease spreader rows (Adhikari et al. 2009; Yang et al. 2010). The same material underwent

140 genotyping-by-sequencing (GBS) characterization according to Elshire et al. (2011) method as
141 described in Książkiewicz et al. (2017). A genomic prediction model was set up on the basis of
142 intra-population predictions estimated via on cross-validations with 10% validation fraction,
143 averaged across 20 repetitions outputted by two possible models, rrBLUP and Bayesian Lasso,
144 using the R package GROAN (Nazzicari and Biscarini 2017). The best-predictive model, as
145 correlation between predicted and observed values based on cross-validation for the RIL
146 population, was applied to an independent set of 384 landrace accessions originating from across
147 the Mediterranean, East Africa, Madeira and the Canaries islands, selected from a diverse
148 collection described in Annicchiarico et al. (2010). SNP-generated markers were obtained for this
149 material using the same procedure described for the model training set. Concurrently, we used
150 Książkiewicz et al.'s (2017) information on SNP markers closely linked to the three QTLs for
151 anthracnose resistance, namely, marker TP222136 for antr04/05_1 on linkage group ALB02,
152 markers TP61122 and TP26007 for antr04/05_2 on linkage group ALB04, and markers TP251482,
153 TP252015 and TP1928 for antr05_3 on linkage group ALB10, to infer the allelic value of these
154 QTLs in the landrace genotypes.

155 **Plant material.** A total of 40 white lupin (*L. albus*) cultivars, breeding lines and landraces
156 were collected from different sources and will be referred to as accessions throughout this
157 publication (**Table 1**). Fifteen accessions were selected based on their contrasting predicted
158 disease scores and because they represented different allelic combinations with three useful
159 QTLs (two accessions), two useful QTLs (antr04/05_1 + antr05_3 for three accessions;
160 antr04/05_1 + antr04/05_2 for one accession), one useful QTL (antr04/05_1 for three accessions;
161 antr05_3 for three accessions), or no useful QTL (three accessions). The rest of the accessions

162 was selected based on their field performance in 2015 to 2017 (C. Arncken, personal
163 communication). All accessions were phenotyped for anthracnose resistance under controlled
164 conditions and 26 accessions were phenotyped under field conditions in a 1-row setup, from
165 which eleven accessions were also phenotyped in field plots. The commercial cultivar Feodora
166 served as reference throughout all phenotyping assays.

167 **Controlled condition experiments.** For high-throughput resistance phenotyping under
168 controlled conditions, one seed per pot was sown in 0.2 liter pots with a diameter of 6 cm,
169 containing non-sterilized peat soil (Einheitserde® Classic, Einheitserdewerke Werkverband e.V.,
170 Sinnatal-Altengronau, Germany) and vermiculite (ISOLA Vermiculite AG, Bözen, Switzerland) in a
171 ratio of 5 to 1. Pots were placed in a growth chamber ($25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, 16 h light and ~70% relative
172 humidity). *C. lupini* JA01 (or IMI 375715) was grown on PDA for 6 to 8 days at 22°C in the dark.
173 Spores were harvested with a sterile spreader after flooding the Petri dish with 2 ml sterile ddH₂O.
174 The concentration was determined using a haemocytometer (0.1 mm; Marienfeld, Lauda-
175 Königshofen, Germany) and adjusted to 10^5 spores/ml. Stem inoculation, inspired by protocols
176 described by Falconi et al. (2015) and Dubrulle et al. (2020b), was performed on 14 day old
177 seedlings (3-4 leaf stage) by carefully puncturing the apical main stem with a sterile syringe
178 needle followed by application of 5 μl spore suspension. Control plants were inoculated with 5
179 μl sterile ddH₂O. After inoculation, plants were incubated for 48 hours at 100% relative humidity
180 (16 h light, 22°C) before being returned to the growth chamber. Plants were watered every three
181 days with 30 ml per plant, and fertilized twice with 100 ml Universal-Flüssigdünger (Gebr. Mayer
182 Produktions- und Vertriebs. GmbH, Wahrenholz, Germany) at two and eight days post

183 inoculation (dpi). The experiments were performed in a randomized complete block design with
184 a minimum of five replicates per experiment.

185 **Field experiments.** Field experiments were performed in Switzerland at site F (Feldbach,
186 47°14'20.0"N 8°47'18.8"E) and site M (Mellikon) in 2018 and 2019 within 6-row plots. Plot sizes
187 in Mellikon were 1.5 x 5 m and in Feldbach 1.5 x 2.7 m with a seed density of 65 seeds/m². Total
188 field trial size in Mellikon 2019 was 608 m², in 2018 450 m², in Feldbach 2019 146 m² and in 2018
189 243 m². Plot experiments relied on natural infection and were performed in a randomized
190 complete block design with three replicates in 2019 and eight replicates in 2018. In addition, a
191 high-throughput 1-row setup was used at both sites in 2019 with two replicates in a randomized
192 complete block design according to a protocol described by Adhikari et al. (2009). Accessions
193 were sown in 1 m rows containing eight plants, with every second row sown with the susceptible
194 cultivar Amiga containing natural seed infection as disease spreader rows. Seeds were sown at
195 the end of March and harvested in mid-August. Before sowing, seeds were inoculated with
196 *Bradyrhizobium sp. lupini* (HiStick[®]L, BASF, UK) and no fertilizer was applied during the growing
197 season.

198 **Disease assessment.** Under controlled conditions, disease phenotypes were assessed at
199 4, 8 and 12 dpi (18, 22 and 26 days after sowing) using a 1 to 9 disease score index (DSI) based
200 on a protocol described by Thomas et al. (2008b): 1 = healthy plant, lesion size is 0 to 5% of stem
201 length; 2 = minor disease symptoms, minor petiole elongation and slight yellowing of older
202 leaves, lesion size is 5 to 15% of stem length; 3 = minor disease symptoms, increased petiole
203 elongation and yellowing of older leaves, lesion size is 15 to 30% of stem length; 4 = moderate
204 disease symptoms, main stem and petiole elongation, minor leaf and stem twisting, leaves are

205 yellowing, lesion size is 30 to 45% of stem length; 5 = moderate disease symptoms, whole plant
206 starts to wilt, leaves and stem start twisting, main stem on the verge of collapsing, lesion is
207 starting to sporulate and its size is 45 to 60% of stem length; 6 = severe disease symptoms, plant
208 has collapsed, severe leaf wilting but plant still has a few green leaves, lesion is sporulating and
209 the size is 60 to 70% of stem length; 7 = severe disease symptoms, plant has completely wilted
210 and only the youngest leaves have not dried out, the lesion is sporulating and the size is 70 to
211 80% of stem length; 8 = very severe disease symptoms, plant has completely wilted and dried
212 out, lesion shows abundant sporulation and its size is 80 to 90% of stem length and 9 = complete
213 plant decay, lesion size is 90 to 100% of stem length (illustrated in **Figure 1A**). The controlled
214 conditions standardized area under the disease progress curve (sAUDPC_{CC}) was calculated to
215 assess and compare disease progression (Jeger and Viljanen-Rollinson 2001; Madden et al. 2007).
216 Although disease scores obtained at single time points gave similar results as sAUDPC (**Table S1**),
217 the sAUDPC was preferred to account for potential biases. At 12 dpi, lesion size, stem length and
218 shoot dry weight were determined. Lesion size is expressed relative to overall stem length
219 ($Lesion_{rel}$) and shoot dry weight is expressed relative to control (SDW_{rel}).

220 Disease assessments in the field were performed using a 1 to 9 DSI based on a protocol
221 described by Jacob et al. (2017): 1 = no disease symptoms (0%), 2 = very minor disease symptoms
222 (>0 to 2% diseased plants), 3 = minor disease symptoms (>2 to 5% diseased plants), 4 = low to
223 moderate disease symptoms (>5 to 8% diseased plants), 5 = moderate disease symptoms (>8 to
224 14% diseased plants), 6 = moderate to severe disease symptoms (>14 to 22% diseased plants), 7
225 = severe disease symptoms (>22 to 37% diseased plants), 8 = severe to extremely severe disease
226 symptoms (>37 to 61% diseased plants), 9 = extremely severe disease symptoms (>61% to 100%

227 diseased plants). In field plots anthracnose occurs in disease foci as illustrated in **Figure 1B**.
228 Disease assessments were performed at least 4 times per growing season, (60 to 70 days 80 to
229 90 days, 100 to 110 days and 120 to 130 days after sowing) and sAUDPC for field plots
230 (sAUDPC_{Field}) and for 1-rows (sAUDPC_{Row}) was calculated to assess and compare disease
231 progression. Yield (dt/ha) was assessed for field plots at grain harvest in August. The two high-
232 throughput phenotyping systems, controlled condition and 1-row field, were compared with field
233 plot disease assessments.

234 **Statistical analysis of experimental data.** Statistical analyses were performed with R 4.0.3
235 (R Core Team 2020) using the packages *lme4* (Bates et al. 2014), *lmerTest* (Kuznetsova et al. 2017)
236 and *emmeans* (Lenth et al. 2019), following a mixed model with factors of interest (i.e. accession,
237 strain) as fixed and environment, environment x accession and replicated block nested in
238 environment as random factor, after confirming the assumptions of normality of residuals and
239 homogeneity of variance. To achieve a normal distribution, data was transformed with a square
240 root or logit transformation. Data are presented as estimated least-squares means using the
241 aforementioned mixed model. Mean separation between lupin accessions and the reference
242 cultivar Feodora was analyzed using Dunnett's test ($p \leq 0.05$). Estimated means of controlled and
243 field conditions were correlated using the Pearson correlation coefficient. Broad sense
244 heritability (H^2) was estimated as: genotypic variance/phenotypic variance, according to (Toker
245 2004). The number of replicates (n) needed to obtain a least significant difference (LSD) of 1 for
246 $\alpha=0.05$ was calculated according to (Williams and Abdi 2010), with the formula below with
247 n =replicates, MSE =mean square error, df =degrees of freedom of residuals, t =t-test distribution
248 and α =critical p-value: $n = (t_{\alpha,df})^2 * 2MSE$

249 Results

250 **Evaluation of phenotyping under controlled conditions.** BLASTn analysis of the ITS region
251 confirmed that Swiss strain JA01 (GenBank accession MT741840) belongs to the species
252 *Colletotrichum lupini*, showing 100% sequence identity with *C. lupini* strains corresponding to
253 genetic group 2 (var. *setosum*; GenBank accessions JQ948169, JQ948161, MK463733) and
254 99.80% (494/495 bp) sequence identity with *C. lupini* strains corresponding to genetic group 1
255 (var. *lupini*; GenBank accessions JQ948155, JQ948159, JQ948158) at 100% query coverage.
256 Comparing the three disease parameters, the highest broad-sense heritability (H^2) was found for
257 standardized area under the disease progress curve under controlled conditions (sAUDPC_{CC}) with
258 a H^2 of 0.82 followed by relative shoot dry weight (SDW_{rel}) with a H^2 of 0.78 and relative lesion
259 size (Lesion_{rel}) with a H^2 of 0.75. Stem inoculation proved to be feasible for high-throughput
260 phenotyping as up to 108 plants per m² could be phenotyped by one person within 26 days. To
261 detect a least significant sAUDPC_{CC} difference of 1 between two genotypes, a minimum of 4
262 replications was required, in contrast to single-row analysis with a H^2 of 0.48 which required 15
263 replicates.

264 **Increased levels of anthracnose resistance identified in white lupin.** Disease
265 phenotyping under controlled conditions revealed quantitative, rather than qualitative disease
266 resistance as none of the 40 phenotyped white lupin accessions showed complete resistance to
267 anthracnose. Eight accessions (Leb01, Eth01, Ares, NL01, Blu-25, Frieda, Eth02 and Kiev Mutant)
268 showed significantly lower sAUDPC_{CC} means compared with the susceptible reference cultivar
269 Feodora, with differences ranging between -1.8 (Leb01) and -1 (Kiev Mutant; **Figure 2A**). The
270 accessions Frieda, Eth01 and Blu-25 also were more resistant under field conditions (**Figure 2C**).

271 The difference between the sAUDPC_{cc} means of accession Hetman and Feodora tended towards
272 significance ($p=0.08$). Five of the accessions mentioned above, Frieda, Kiev Mutant, NL01, Blu-25,
273 and Eth01 also showed significantly higher SDW_{rel} means compared with Feodora, with
274 differences ranging between 0.36 (Frieda) and 0.15 (Eth01; **Figure S1A**). The assessment of
275 Lesion_{rel} did not reveal significant differences compared to Feodora (**Figure S2A**).

276 **Strong correlation between controlled condition phenotyping and field performance.** A
277 subset of 11 white lupin accessions was screened in field plots to verify the phenotypes expressed
278 under controlled and 1- row field conditions. Significant genotype ($p=0.01$), field site ($p=0.001$)
279 and genotype x field interaction ($p<0.001$) effects were found for the field plot experiments.
280 Spatial within-trial variation was accounted for by a block effect ($p>0.001$). No significant effects
281 were detected for the 1-row experiments. Disease pressure gradually increased over the growing
282 season and was on average lower in 2018 (3.95) compared to 2019 (4.77). Growing conditions in
283 2018 were warmer (18.35°C) and drier (267 mm) on average, compared to 2019 (16.35°C and 572
284 mm; **Figure S4**). Significant Pearson correlation coefficients were found between sAUDPC_{Field}
285 averaged across all four environments and sAUDPC_{cc} ($r=0.95$, $p<0.0001$), SDW_{rel} ($r=-0.80$, $p=0.003$)
286 and Lesion_{rel} ($r=0.89$, $p<0.0001$; **Table 2, Figure 2, S1 and S2**). For each environment individually,
287 correlations with sAUDPC_{Field} ranged between 0.95 and 0.64 for sAUDPC_{cc}, -0.86 and -0.52 for
288 SDW_{rel} and 0.95 and 0.44 for Lesion_{rel}. When comparing controlled condition parameters with
289 harvested yield (dt/ha) of the field plots averaged across all four environments, a significant
290 correlation of -0.64 ($p=0.03$) was found for sAUDPC_{cc}. Correlations between yield and SDW_{rel}
291 ($r=0.62$, $p=0.04$) and Lesion_{rel} ($r=-0.58$, $p=0.064$) were or tended towards significance. For each
292 environment individually, correlations with yield ranged between -0.79 and -0.22 for sAUDPC_{cc},

293 0.71 and 0.19 for SDW_{rel} and -0.86 and -0.25 for $Lesion_{rel}$. High-throughput disease phenotyping
294 within a 1-row field setup ($sAUDPC_{Row}$) showed Pearson correlation coefficients of 0.33 ($p=0.43$)
295 and -0.23 ($p=0.56$) with $sAUDPC_{Field}$ and yield averaged across all four environments, respectively,
296 when replicated once at one site (**Table 2**). When replicated twice at two sites, Pearson
297 correlations of 0.31 ($p=0.34$) and -0.45 ($p=0.17$) between $sAUDPC_{Field}$ and yield, respectively, were
298 found. Comparing 1-row experiments to each environment individually showed no significant
299 correlations.

300 **Poor genomic predictions.** The best-predicting model was rrBLUP, with a value of 0.50
301 for intra-populations predictive ability. The predicted disease scores ranged from 2.12 to 4.70.
302 The useful QTL *antr04/05_2* on linkage group ALB04 was particularly rare and was only found in
303 eight genotypes. This included two genotypes from Ethiopia, one of which was included in this
304 study (Eth04) and which combined a very low predicted susceptibility score (2.165) with the
305 simultaneous presence of all three QTLs (**Table 1**). Genomic prediction (GP) values generated by
306 rrBLUP (**Table 1**) revealed no significant correlation with $sAUDPC_{CC}$ (-0.31, $p=0.26$) or $sAUDPC_{Row}$
307 values (-0.46, $p=0.085$; **Table 2**). When comparing GP with SDW_{rel} and $Lesion_{rel}$, significant
308 Pearson correlation coefficients of 0.60 ($p=0.02$) and -0.55 ($p=0.03$), respectively, were revealed.
309 Importantly, the parental lines of the RIL population that was used for the QTL study and the
310 genomic prediction model, i.e., P27174 and Kiev Mutant, exhibited an opposite anthracnose
311 resistance pattern to that displayed in their evaluation in Australia (Rychel-Bielska et al. 2020).
312 The resistant parent P27174 ($n=15$) showed a $sAUDPC_{CC}$ of 3.7 and an SDW_{rel} of 0.5, while the
313 susceptible parent Kiev Mutant ($n=23$) showed a $sAUDPC_{CC}$ of 2.9 and an SDW_{rel} of 1 (**Figure 2**,
314 **Figure S1**). This observation was confirmed by a follow-up experiment where Kiev Mutant,

315 P27174, Feodora and four additional lupin accessions, were inoculated with either the Australian
316 *C. lupini* strain IMI 375715 or the Swiss *C. lupini* strain JA01 (**Figure S3**). This experiment also
317 indicated that both *C. lupini* strains exhibit a similar virulence pattern on white lupin as no strain
318 ($p=0.64$) or strain x accession interaction ($p=0.96$) effects were observed.

319

320 Discussion

321 Considering the lack of resistance to anthracnose disease in white lupin, a reliable high-
322 throughput phenotyping tool to screen global white lupin germplasm is required. The described
323 anthracnose disease phenotyping protocol, inoculating the stems of 14 day old white lupin
324 seedlings grown under controlled conditions with a spore suspension of the pathogen, was useful
325 to identify resistant genotypes, feasible for high-throughput phenotyping and the data
326 corresponded with field performance. Similar stem inoculation approaches have proven to be a
327 reliable tool to speed up selection in resistance breeding for various crops such as cotton (Bolek
328 et al. 2005), sunflower (Schwanck et al. 2016), various *Brassicaceae* (Atri et al. 2019), and
329 different legumes such as pea (Chang et al. 2018), soy (Twizeyimana et al. 2012) and Andean
330 lupin (Falconí 2012). This study showed strong significant correlations ($r > 0.8$) between
331 controlled condition phenotyping and replicated multi-environment field evaluations. This is in
332 line with an anthracnose resistance study performed in Canada, showing that disease evaluations
333 of stem inoculated seedlings of six white lupin cultivars under controlled conditions
334 corresponded to disease evaluations of a 3 year field trial (Bhaskara Reddy et al. 1996). High
335 correlations between stem inoculation under controlled conditions and field evaluations were
336 also reported for other crops such as soybean (Twizeyimana et al. 2012), pea (Li 2018), canola
337 (Devey and Rosielle 1986) and grapevine (Poolsawat et al. 2012). Thus, stem inoculation of white
338 lupin seedlings under controlled conditions can be considered a reliable tool to speed up white
339 lupin resistance breeding.

340 From the three disease parameters, sAUDPC_{CC} showed the strongest correlation with field
341 performance ($r = 0.95$, $p < 0.0001$) and the highest heritability ($H^2 = 0.82$). In other plant-

342 pathosystems, using sAUDPC as a disease parameter was also highly correlated to field
343 performance (Bradley et al. 2006; Li 2018; Trapero et al. 2013). The disease parameters SDW_{rel}
344 and $Lesion_{rel}$ also showed high heritability and correlation to field performance, although these
345 were lower than for $sAUDPC_{CC}$. With $lesion_{rel}$, no accessions could be identified that significantly
346 showed less infection than Feodora. Besides resistance, SDW_{rel} has the advantage of also
347 encompassing tolerance (Maya and Matsubara 2013). It should be taken into account, however,
348 that a distinct symptom of lupin anthracnose is shoot elongation, potentially leading to a slight
349 increase in biomass in minor to moderately infected plants at early stages, and therefore
350 potentially leading to a misinterpretation of SDW_{rel} results. Based on $sAUDPC_{CC}$, eight out of the
351 forty accessions were significantly more resistant to anthracnose than the susceptible reference
352 cultivar Feodora (**Figure 2A**). Among those are three released cultivars, Frieda, Ares and Kiev
353 Mutant, the breeding line Blu-25 and four genetic resources, Eth01, Eth02, NL01 and Leb01,
354 which are thus valuable resources for white lupin breeding and cultivation. The developed
355 phenotyping tool should now be applied on a larger set of accessions to find more sources of
356 resistance in white lupin to counter yield loss caused by anthracnose.

357 Disease phenotyping within a 1-row field setup has been widely applied for resistance
358 breeding (Niks et al. 2011), including lupins (Adhikari et al. 2009; Ruge-Wehling et al. 2009). In
359 this study, 1-row disease evaluations based on $sAUDPC_{Row}$, replicated once at one site, showed
360 no significant correlations with field plot evaluations ($sAUDPC_{Field}$). With four replicates over two
361 sites, correlation with $sAUDPC_{Field}$ improved. Compared to stem inoculation under controlled
362 conditions, 1-row disease phenotyping showed a weaker correlation to field performance and
363 results should be interpreted with caution. However, with sufficient replicates, 1-row disease

364 phenotyping could be an alternative approach to identify anthracnose resistance in white lupin,
365 especially when environmental variation has to be considered.

366 Predicted resistance values based on the genomic prediction model reported by Rychel-
367 Bielska et al. (2020), taking into account the three major QTLs and possible minor ones, showed
368 no positive correlations with sAUDPC_{CC} and sAUDPC_{Row}, suggesting no association of the reported
369 QTLs with anthracnose resistance in the current study. As discussed by Rychel-Bielska et al.
370 (2020), different inoculation methods, environmental variation and *C. lupini* strain-specific
371 virulence can influence plant resistance and therefore should be taken into account. In this study,
372 stem inoculation through wounding was performed under controlled conditions and might have
373 contributed to the observed lack of correlation and contrasting resistance levels observed for
374 Kiev Mutant and P27174. This, however, does not explain the absence of positive correlations
375 between 1-row field evaluations under natural infection and the predicted values. In blue lupin,
376 a similar unexpected observation occurred when material with strong anthracnose resistance
377 identified under Australian conditions (Yang et al. 2008) turned out to be susceptible in Germany
378 (Fischer et al. 2015). Warmer temperatures up to 25°C and higher rainfall (mm) favour
379 anthracnose disease pressure in lupin (Dubrulle et al. 2020b; Thomas and Sweetingham 2004),
380 highlighting the relevance of varying environmental conditions. The average growing conditions
381 during the Swiss (16.1 to 18.7°C, 195 to 694 mm, **Figure S4**) and Australian field experiments
382 (12.9 to 13.1°C, 441 to 566 mm, BOM 2005) indicate the lower temperature of 3 to 6 °C on
383 average at the Australian site may have contributed to the observed inconsistencies. Differences
384 in *C. lupini* strain virulence are unlikely as no strain or accession x strain interaction effects were
385 found and *C. lupini* is suggested to be clonal (Dubrulle et al. 2020b; Talhinas et al. 2016).

386 Although QTL mapping and genomic prediction studies for quantitative traits are considered
387 valuable (de Ronne et al. 2020; Haile et al. 2020; Lyra et al. 2020) and are being applied for key
388 traits in white lupin (Annicchiarico et al. 2020; Annicchiarico et al. 2019), the method encounters
389 various limitations (Wang et al. 2018; Xu et al. 2017). Genomic prediction models could
390 effectively be applied to less related populations (Hao et al. 2019), but optimal predictions are
391 achieved with related training populations (Akdemir and Isidro-Sánchez 2019; Albrecht et al.
392 2011; Berro et al. 2019). We suggest the main reason for poor genomic predictions of
393 anthracnose tolerance in this study was the seemingly completely inconsistent response within
394 the current testing conditions of the two parent genotypes that represented resistance and
395 susceptibility in the RIL population evaluated in the Australian site, whose data were used for
396 constructing the genomic model.

397 This study provides a high-throughput phenotyping tool to identify field-relevant
398 resistance against lupin anthracnose under controlled conditions to support white lupin
399 resistance breeding. Phenotyping white lupin germplasm within a 1-row setup under field
400 conditions was deemed to be less reliable as lower correlations with field plot disease
401 assessments were found compared with controlled condition phenotyping. The resistant
402 accessions identified in this study, Frieda, Blu-25, Eth01, Eth02, NL01, Leb01 and Ares, should be
403 incorporated into current breeding programs after field validation. As predicted resistance values
404 could not be validated, further insight on the effect of environmental conditions, infection
405 pathways and the genetic basis underlying anthracnose resistance in white lupin is required.
406 Current research focuses on phenotyping and genotyping a diverse set of 200 white lupin

407 genotypes, including Kiev Mutant, P27174 and the resistant accessions identified in this study
408 using the described phenotyping tool.

409

410

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419

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428

429 Literature Cited

- 430 Adhikari, K., Buirchell, B., Thomas, G. J., Sweetingham, M. W., and Yang, H. 2009. Identification of
431 anthracnose resistance in *Lupinus albus* L. and its transfer from landraces to modern cultivars.
432 Crop and Pasture Science 60:472-479.
- 433 Adhikari, K. N., Thomas, G., Buirchell, B. J., and Sweetingham, M. W. 2011. Identification of anthracnose
434 resistance in yellow lupin (*Lupinus luteus* L.) and its incorporation into breeding lines. Plant
435 breeding 130:660-664.
- 436 Agrometeo. 2019. Agrometeo, Swiss Federation. <http://www.agrometeo.ch/de/meteorology/datas>
437 (accessed 11/06/2020)
- 438 Akdemir, D., and Isidro-Sánchez, J. 2019. Design of training populations for selective phenotyping in
439 genomic prediction. Scientific reports 9:1-15.
- 440 Albrecht, T., Wimmer, V., Auinger, H. J., Erbe, M., Knaak, C., Ouzunova, M., Simianer, H., and Schön, C. C.
441 2011. Genome-based prediction of testcross values in maize. Theoretical and Applied Genetics
442 123:339.
- 443 Annicchiarico, P., Harzic, N., and Carroni, A. M. 2010. Adaptation, diversity, and exploitation of global
444 white lupin (*Lupinus albus* L.) landrace genetic resources. Field Crops Research 119:114-124.
- 445 Annicchiarico, P., Romani, M., and Pecetti, L. 2018. White lupin (*Lupinus albus*) variation for adaptation
446 to severe drought stress. Plant Breeding 137:782-789.
- 447 Annicchiarico, P., Nazzicari, N., and Ferrari, B. 2020. Genetic and genomic resources in white Lupin and
448 the application of genomic selection. The Lupin Genome: 139-149. Springer.
- 449 Annicchiarico, P., Nazzicari, N., Ferrari, B., Harzic, N., Carroni, A. M., Romani, M., and Pecetti, L. 2019.
450 Genomic prediction of grain yield in contrasting environments for white lupin genetic resources.
451 Molecular Breeding 39:142.
- 452 Arnoldi, A., Boschini, G., Zanoni, C., and Lammi, C. 2015. The health benefits of sweet lupin seed flours
453 and isolated proteins. Journal of Functional Foods 18:550-563.
- 454 Atri, C., Akhtar, J., Gupta, M., Gupta, N., Goyal, A., Rana, K., Kaur, R., Mittal, M., Sharma, A., and Singh,
455 M. P. 2019. Molecular and genetic analysis of defensive responses of *Brassica juncea*-*B.*
456 *fruticulosa* introgression lines to *Sclerotinia* infection. Scientific reports 9:1-12.
- 457 Bates, D., Mächler, M., Bolker, B., and Walker, S. 2014. Fitting linear mixed-effects models using lme4.
458 arXiv preprint arXiv:1406.5823.
- 459 Berro, I., Lado, B., Nalin, R. S., Quincke, M., and Gutiérrez, L. 2019. Training population optimization for
460 genomic selection. The Plant Genome 12:1-14.
- 461 Bhaskara Reddy, M., Atlin, G., and Paulitz, T. 1996. Response of white lupine cultivars to *Phoma* sp. and
462 *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides*. Canadian Journal of Plant Pathology 18:272-278.
- 463 Bolek, Y., Bell, A., El-Zik, K., Thaxton, P., and Magill, C. 2005. Reaction of cotton cultivars and an F2
464 population to stem inoculation with isolates *Verticillium dahliae*. Journal of Phytopathology
465 153:269-273.
- 466 BOM. 2005. Bureau of Meteorology of Australian Government.
467 <http://www.bom.gov.au/climate/data/index.shtml> (accessed 11/06/2020)
- 468 Boschini, G., Annicchiarico, P., Resta, D., D'Agostina, A., and Arnoldi, A. 2008. Quinolizidine alkaloids in
469 seeds of lupin genotypes of different origins. Journal of agricultural and food chemistry 56:3657-
470 3663.
- 471 Bradley, C., Henson, R., Porter, P. M., LeGare, D., Del Rio, L., and Khot, S. 2006. Response of canola
472 cultivars to *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum* in controlled and field environments. Plant disease 90:215-
473 219.
- 474 Breiman, L. 2001. Random forests. Machine learning 45:5-32.

- 475 Chang, H. X., Sang, H., Wang, J., McPhee, K. E., Zhuang, X., Porter, L. D., and Chilvers, M. I. 2018.
 476 Exploring the genetics of lesion and nodal resistance in pea (*Pisum sativum* L.) to *Sclerotinia*
 477 *sclerotiorum* using genome-wide association studies and RNA-Seq. *Plant direct* 2:e00064.
- 478 Cowling, W., Buirchell, B., Sweetingham, M., Yang, H., Thomas, G., Lockett, D., Brown, A., and Hamblin, J.
 479 2000. Anthracnose resistance in lupins-an innovative Australian research effort 1996-1998.
 480 Pages 60-62 in: *Lupin, an ancient crop for the new millennium: Proceedings of the 9th*
 481 *International Lupin Conference, Klink/Muritz, Germany, 20-24 June, 1999. International Lupin*
 482 *Association.*
- 483 Damm, U., Cannon, P. F., Woudenberg, J. H. C., and Crous, P. W. 2012. The *Colletotrichum acutatum*
 484 *species complex. Studies in Mycology* 73:37-113.
- 485 de Ronne, M., Labbé, C., Lebreton, A., Sonah, H., Deshmukh, R., Jean, M., Belzile, F., O'Donoghue, L.,
 486 and Bélanger, R. 2020. Integrated QTL mapping, gene expression and nucleotide variation
 487 analyses to investigate complex quantitative traits: a case study with the soybean-*Phytophthora*
 488 *sojae* interaction. *Plant biotechnology journal* 18:1492-1494.
- 489 De Silva, D. D., Crous, P. W., Ades, P. K., Hyde, K. D., and Taylor, P. W. 2017. Life styles of *Colletotrichum*
 490 *species and implications for plant biosecurity. Fungal Biology Reviews* 31:155-168.
- 491 Devey, M., and Rosielle, A. 1986. Relationship between field and greenhouse ratings for tolerance to
 492 *Verticillium* wilt on cotton 1. *Crop science* 26:1-4.
- 493 Dubrulle, G., Picot, A., Madec, S., Corre, E., Pawtowski, A., Baroncelli, R., Zivy, M., Balliau, T., Le Floch, G.,
 494 and Pensec, F. 2020a. Deciphering the infectious process of *Colletotrichum lupini* in lupin
 495 through transcriptomic and proteomic analysis. *Microorganisms* 8:1621.
- 496 Dubrulle, G., Pensec, F., Picot, A., Rigalma, K., Pawtowski, A., Nicolleau, S., Harzic, N., Nodet, P.,
 497 Baroncelli, R., and Le Floch, G. 2020b. Phylogenetic diversity and effect of temperature on
 498 pathogenicity of *Colletotrichum lupini*. *Plant Disease* 104:938-950.
- 499 Elshire, R. J., Glaubitz, J. C., Sun, Q., Poland, J. A., Kawamoto, K., Buckler, E. S., and Mitchell, S. E. 2011. A
 500 robust, simple genotyping-by-sequencing (GBS) approach for high diversity species. *PloS one*
 501 6:e19379.
- 502 Falconí, C. 2012. *Lupinus mutabilis* in Ecuador with special emphasis on anthracnose resistance.
- 503 Falconi, C. E., Visser, R. G., and van Heusden, S. 2015. Influence of plant growth stage on resistance to
 504 anthracnose in Andean lupin (*Lupinus mutabilis*). *Crop and Pasture Science* 66:729-734.
- 505 FAOSTAT. 2017. Statistics Division of the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
 506 <http://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QC> (accessed 16/11/2019).
- 507 Fernández-Pascual, M., Pueyo, J. J., Felipe, M., Golvano, M. P., and Lucas, M. M. 2007. Singular features
 508 of the *Bradyrhizobium-Lupinus* symbiosis.
- 509 Fischer, K., Dieterich, R., Nelson, M. N., Kamphuis, L. G., Singh, K. B., Rotter, B., Krezdorn, N., Winter, P.,
 510 Wehling, P., and Ruge-Wehling, B. 2015. Characterization and mapping of *LanrBo*: a locus
 511 conferring anthracnose resistance in narrow-leaved lupin (*Lupinus angustifolius* L.). *Theoretical*
 512 *and applied genetics* 128:2121-2130.
- 513 Gallardo, C., Hufnagel, B., Casset, C., Alcon, C., Garcia, F., Divol, F., Marquès, L., Dumas, P., and Péret, B.
 514 2019. Anatomical and hormonal description of rootlet primordium development along white
 515 lupin cluster root. *Physiologia plantarum* 165:4-16.
- 516 Gresta, F., Wink, M., Prins, U., Abberton, M., Capraro, J., Scarafoni, A., & Hill, G. 2017. Lupins in
 517 European cropping systems. *Legumes in cropping systems* 6:88-108 in: F. L. S. D. Murphy-Bokern
 518 and C. A. Watson, eds. *The Centre for Agriculture and Bioscience International.*
- 519 Haile, J. K., N'Diaye, A., Sari, E., Walkowiak, S., Rutkoski, J. E., Kutcher, H. R., and Pozniak, C. J. 2020.
 520 Potential of genomic selection and integrating "Omics" data for disease evaluation in wheat.
- 521 Hall, T. 2004. BioEdit version 7.0. 0. Distributed by the author, website:
 522 www.mbio.ncsu.edu/BioEdit/bioedit.html.

- 523 Hao, Y., Wang, H., Yang, X., Zhang, H., He, C., Li, D., Li, H., Wang, G., Wang, J., and Fu, J. 2019. Genomic
524 prediction using existing historical data contributing to selection in biparental populations: A
525 study of kernel oil in maize. *The Plant Genome* 12:1-9.
- 526 Heffner, E. L., Sorrells, M. E., and Jannink, J. L. 2009. Genomic selection for crop improvement. *Crop*
527 *Science* 49:1-12.
- 528 Henchion, M., Hayes, M., Mullen, A. M., Fenelon, M., and Tiwari, B. 2017. Future protein supply and
529 demand: strategies and factors influencing a sustainable equilibrium. *Foods* 6:53.
- 530 Jacob, I., Feuerstein, U., Heinz, M., Schott, M., and Urbatzka, P. 2017. Evaluation of new breeding lines
531 of white lupin with improved resistance to anthracnose. *Euphytica* 213:236.
- 532 Jeger, M., and Viljanen-Rollinson, S. 2001. The use of the area under the disease-progress curve (AUDPC)
533 to assess quantitative disease resistance in crop cultivars. *Theoretical and Applied Genetics*
534 102:32-40.
- 535 Książkiewicz, M., Nazzicari, N., Yang, H. a., Nelson, M. N., Renshaw, D., Rychel, S., Ferrari, B., Carelli, M.,
536 Tomaszewska, M., and Stawiński, S. 2017. A high-density consensus linkage map of white lupin
537 highlights synteny with narrow-leaved lupin and provides markers tagging key agronomic traits.
538 *Scientific reports* 7:15335.
- 539 Kuznetsova, A., Brockhoff, P. B., and Christensen, R. H. 2017. lmerTest package: tests in linear mixed
540 effects models. *Journal of statistical software* 82:1-26.
- 541 Lambers, H., Clements, J. C., and Nelson, M. N. 2013. How a phosphorus-acquisition strategy based on
542 carboxylate exudation powers the success and agronomic potential of lupines (*Lupinus*,
543 *Fabaceae*). *American Journal of Botany* 100:263-288.
- 544 Lenth, R., Singmann, H., Love, J., Buerkner, P., and Herve, M. 2019. emmeans: Estimated Marginal
545 Means, aka Least-Squares Means (Version 1.3. 4).
- 546 Li, S. 2018. Development of a seedling inoculation technique for rapid evaluation of soybean for
547 resistance to *Phomopsis longicolla* under controlled conditions. *Plant methods* 14:81.
- 548 Lucas, M. M., Stoddard, F. L., Annicchiarico, P., Frias, J., Martinez-Villaluenga, C., Sussmann, D., Duranti,
549 M., Seger, A., Zander, P. M., and Pueyo, J. J. 2015. The future of lupin as a protein crop in
550 Europe. *Frontiers in plant science* 6:705.
- 551 Lyra, D. H., Virlet, N., Sadeghi-Tehran, P., Hassall, K. L., Wingen, L. U., Orford, S., Griffiths, S., Hawkesford,
552 M. J., and Slavov, G. T. 2020. Functional QTL mapping and genomic prediction of canopy height
553 in wheat measured using a robotic field phenotyping platform. *Journal of experimental botany*
554 71:1885-1898.
- 555 Madden, L. V., Hughes, G., and Van Den Bosch, F. 2007. The study of plant disease epidemics.
- 556 Maya, M. A., and Matsubara, Y.-i. 2013. Tolerance to *Fusarium* wilt and anthracnose diseases and
557 changes of antioxidative activity in mycorrhizal cyclamen. *Crop protection* 47:41-48.
- 558 Minas, K., McEwan, N. R., Newbold, C. J., and Scott, K. P. 2011. Optimization of a high-throughput CTAB-
559 based protocol for the extraction of qPCR-grade DNA from rumen fluid, plant and bacterial pure
560 cultures. *FEMS microbiology letters* 325:162-169.
- 561 Monteiro, M. R. P., Costa, A. B. P., Campos, S. F., Silva, M. R., da Silva, C. O., Martino, H. S. D., and
562 Silvestre, M. P. C. 2014. Evaluation of the chemical composition, protein quality and digestibility
563 of lupin (*Lupinus albus* and *Lupinus angustifolius*). *O Mundo da Saúde, São Paulo* 38:251-259.
- 564 Nazzicari, N., and Biscarini, F. 2017. GROAN: Genomic regression workbench (version 1.0. 0).
- 565 Niks, R. E., Parlevliet, J., Lindhout, P., and Bai, Y. 2011. Breeding crops with resistance to diseases and
566 pests. Wageningen Academic Publishers.
- 567 Nirenberg, H. I., Feiler, U., and Hagedorn, G. 2002. Description of *Colletotrichum lupini* comb. nov. in
568 modern terms. *Mycologia* 94:307-320.
- 569 Pagano, M. C., and Miransari, M. 2016. The importance of soybean production worldwide. Pages 1-26 in:
570 Abiotic and biotic stresses in soybean production. Elsevier.

- 571 Peix, A., Ramírez-Bahena, M. H., Flores-Félix, J. D., de la Vega, P. A., Rivas, R., Mateos, P. F., Iguar, J. M.,
572 Martínez-Molina, E., Trujillo, M. E., and Velázquez, E. 2015. Revision of the taxonomic status of
573 the species *Rhizobium lupini* and reclassification as *Bradyrhizobium lupini* comb. nov.
574 International journal of systematic and evolutionary microbiology 65:1213-1219.
- 575 Peres, N. A., Timmer, L. W., Adaskaveg, J. E., and Correll, J. C. 2005. Lifest styles of *Colletotrichum*
576 *acutatum*. Plant Disease 89:784-796.
- 577 Phan, H. T. T., Ellwood, S. R., Adhikari, K., Nelson, M. N., and Oliver, R. P. 2007. The first genetic and
578 comparative map of white Lupin (*Lupinus albus* L.): Identification of QTLs for anthracnose
579 resistance and flowering time, and a locus for alkaloid content. DNA Research 14:59-70.
- 580 Poolsawat, O., Tharapreuksapong, A., Wongkaew, S., Chaowiset, W., and Tantasawat, P. 2012.
581 Laboratory and field evaluations of resistance to *Sphaceloma ampelinum* causing anthracnose in
582 grapevine. Australasian Plant Pathology 41:263-269.
- 583 Raman, R., Cowley, R. B., Raman, H., and Luckett, D. J. 2014. Analyses using SSR and DArT molecular
584 markers reveal that Ethiopian accessions of white Lupin (*Lupinus albus* L.) represent a unique
585 genepool. Open Journal of Genetics 04:87-98.
- 586 Ruge-Wehling, B., Dieterich, R., Thiele, C., Eickmeyer, F., Wehling, P., and others. 2009. Resistance to
587 anthracnose in narrow-leaved lupin (*Lupinus angustifolius* L.): Sources of resistance and
588 development of molecular markers. Journal fur Kulturpflanzen-Journal of Cultivated Plants
589 61:62.
- 590 Rychel-Bielska, S., Nazzicari, N., Plewiński, P., Bielski, W., Annicchiarico, P., and Książkiewicz, M. 2020.
591 Development of PCR-based markers and whole-genome selection model for anthracnose
592 resistance in white lupin (*Lupinus albus* L.). Journal of Applied Genetics: **61**, 531–545.
- 593 Schwanck, A., Savary, S., Lepennetier, A., Debaeke, P., Vincourt, P., and Willocquet, L. 2016. Predicting
594 quantitative host plant resistance against phoma black stem in sunflower. Plant Pathology
595 65:1366-1379.
- 596 Talhinhos, P., Baroncelli, R., and Le Floch, G. 2016. Anthracnose of lupins caused by *Colletotrichum*
597 *lupini*: a recent disease and a successful worldwide pathogen. Journal of Plant Pathology 98:5-
598 14.
- 599 R Core Team. 2020. R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing. 467.
- 600 Thomas, G., and Sweetingham, M. 2004. Cultivar and environment influence the development of lupin
601 anthracnose caused by *Colletotrichum lupini*. Australasian plant pathology 33:571-577.
- 602 Thomas, G., Sweetingham, M., and Adcock, K. 2008a. Application of fungicides to reduce yield loss in
603 anthracnose-infected lupins. Crop Protection 27:1071-1077.
- 604 Thomas, G., Sweetingham, M., Yang, H., and Speijers, J. 2008b. Effect of temperature on growth of
605 *Colletotrichum lupini* and on anthracnose infection and resistance in lupins. Australasian Plant
606 Pathology 37:35-39.
- 607 Toker, C. 2004. Estimates of broad-sense heritability for seed yield and yield criteria in faba bean (*Vicia*
608 *faba* L.). Hereditas 140:222-225.
- 609 Trapero, C., Díez, C. M., Rallo, L., Barranco, D., and López-Escudero, F. J. 2013. Effective inoculation
610 methods to screen for resistance to *Verticillium* wilt in olive. Scientia horticultrae 162:252-259.
- 611 Twizeyimana, M., Hill, C., Pawlowski, M., Paul, C., and Hartman, G. L. 2012. A cut-stem inoculation
612 technique to evaluate soybean for resistance to *Macrophomina phaseolina*. Plant disease
613 96:1210-1215.
- 614 von Baer, E. 2009. Pecos-Baer: A new cultivar of white lupin with determined bushy growth habit,
615 sweet grain and high protein content. Chilean Journal of Agricultural Research 69:577-580.
- 616 Wang, X., Xu, Y., Hu, Z., and Xu, C. 2018. Genomic selection methods for crop improvement: Current
617 status and prospects. The Crop Journal 6:330-340.

- 618 White, T. J., Bruns, T., Lee, S., and Taylor, J. 1990. Amplification and direct sequencing of fungal
619 ribosomal RNA genes for phylogenetics. PCR protocols: a guide to methods and applications
620 18:315-322.
- 621 White, P., French, B., McLarty, A., and Grains Research and Development Corporation. 2008. Producing
622 lupins. 2 ed. Department of Agriculture and Food, Western Australia, Perth.
- 623 Williams, L. J., and Abdi, H. 2010. Fisher's least significant difference (LSD) test. Encyclopedia of research
624 design 218:840-853.
- 625 Xu, Y., Li, P., Yang, Z., and Xu, C. 2017. Genetic mapping of quantitative trait loci in crops. The Crop
626 Journal 5:175-184.
- 627 Yang, H., Boersma, J. G., You, M., Buirchell, B. J., and Sweetingham, M. W. 2004. Development and
628 implementation of a sequence-specific PCR marker linked to a gene conferring resistance to
629 anthracnose disease in narrow-leaved lupin (*Lupinus angustifolius* L.). Molecular Breeding
630 14:145-151.
- 631 Yang, H., Renshaw, D., Thomas, G., Buirchell, B., and Sweetingham, M. 2008. A strategy to develop
632 molecular markers applicable to a wide range of crosses for marker assisted selection in plant
633 breeding: a case study on anthracnose disease resistance in lupin (*Lupinus angustifolius* L.).
634 Molecular breeding 21:473-483.
- 635 Yang, H., Lin, R., Renshaw, D., Li, C., Adhikari, K., Thomas, G., Buirchell, B., Sweetingham, M., and Yan, G.
636 2010. Development of sequence-specific PCR markers associated with a polygenic controlled
637 trait for marker-assisted selection using a modified selective genotyping strategy: a case study
638 on anthracnose disease resistance in white lupin (*Lupinus albus* L.). Molecular Breeding 25:239-
639 249.

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641

642 **Table 1.** Origins and characteristics of white lupin (*Lupinus albus*) accessions phenotyped for
 643 anthracnose (*Colletotrichum lupini*) resistance in this study.

<i>Accession</i>	<i>Origin</i>	<i>Genbank code</i>	<i>Institution</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>GP</i>	<i>QTL</i> <i>b</i>	<i>n</i>
Mut28^a	-	LUP 6445	IPK (Germany)	Genetic Resource	-	-	10
Cro01^a	Yugoslavia	LUP 237	IPK (Germany)	Genetic Resource	-	-	15
Eth01^a	Ethiopia	LUP 2078	IPK (Germany)	Genetic Resource	-	-	10
Frieda^a	Germany	Frieda	DSV (Germany)	Cultivar	-	-	19
Sulimo^{*a}	France	Sulimo	Jouffrai-Drillaud (France)	Cultivar	-	-	11
Blu-25^{*a}	Chile	Blu-25	Semillas Baer (Chile)	Breeding line	-	-	26
Feodora^{*a}	France	Feodora	Jouffrai-Drillaud (France)	Cultivar	-	-	37
Amiga^{*a}	France	Amiga	Florimond-Desprez (France)	Cultivar	-	-	20
Figaro^{*a}	France	Figaro	Jouffrai-Drillaud (France)	Cultivar	-	-	8
Zulika^{*a}	Czech Republic	Zulika	Oseva s.r.o. (Czech Republic)	Cultivar	-	-	7
Dieta^{*a}	UK	Dieta	Soya UK (UK)	Cultivar	-	-	8
KievMutant	Ukraine	95413	Polish Genebank (Poland)	Cultivar	-	-	23
P27175	Ethiopia	P27175	DPIRD (Australia)	Landrace	-	-	18
P27174	Ethiopia	P27174	DPIRD (Australia)	Landrace	-	-	15
Alg01	Algeria	La 572	CREA (Italy)	Genetic Resource	-	-	10
Eth02	Ethiopia	LUP 258	IPK (Germany)	Genetic Resource	-	-	11
Eth03	Ethiopia	LUP 2076	IPK (Germany)	Genetic Resource	-	-	6
NL01 ^c	The Netherlands ^c	LUP 2079	IPK (Germany)	Genetic Resource	-	-	10
Egy01	Egypt	503	Vavilov Research Institute (Russia)	Genetic Resource	-	-	6
MuPI	-	LUP 2104	IPK (Germany)	Genetic Resource	-	-	6
EdwBra	The Netherlands	V11-12-6	Louis Bolk Institute (NL)	Breeding line	-	-	6
Bianca	Italy	LUP 238	IPK (Germany)	Cultivar	-	-	6

Andro	Australia	Andromeda	DPIRD (Australia)	Cultivar	-	-	10
Hetman	-	LUP 6449	IPK (Germany)	Cultivar	-	-	12
Spn01	Spain	-	Local market (Spain)	-	-	-	6
Eth04 ^a	Ethiopia	LAP0084	CREA (Italy)	Genetic	2.1	1,1,1	7
				Resource	7		
Isr01 ^a	Israel	LAP0071	CREA (Italy)	Genetic	3.5	1,1,1	7
				Resource			
Egy02 ^a	Egypt	LAP0093	CREA (Italy)	Genetic	3.3	1,0,1	7
				Resource	1		
Can01 ^a	Canaries	LAP0063	CREA (Italy)	Genetic	3.4	1,0,1	8
				Resource	6		
Leb01 ^a	Lebanon	LAP0070	CREA (Italy)	Genetic	3.5	1,0,1	8
				Resource	6		
Ita01 ^a	Italy	LAP0098	CREA (Italy)	Genetic	2.6	1,1,0	8
				Resource	9		
Ita02 ^a	Italy	LAP0101	CREA (Italy)	Genetic	3.5	1,0,0	6
				Resource	1		
Ita03 ^a	Italy	LAP0099	CREA (Italy)	Genetic	3.6	1,0,0	6
				Resource	9		
Ita04 ^a	Italy	LAP0107	CREA (Italy)	Genetic	3.1	1,0,0	8
				Resource	7		
Sud01 ^a	Sudan	LAP0082	CREA (Italy)	Genetic	3.5	0,0,1	7
				Resource	7		
Mor01 ^a	Morocco	LAP0055	CREA (Italy)	Genetic	3.8	0,0,1	8
				Resource	6		
Ares ^a	France	Ares	CREA (Italy)	Cultivar	4.6	0,0,1	7
Ita05 ^a	Italy	LAP0097	CREA (Italy)	Genetic	3.7	0,0,0	8
				Resource	9		
Leb02 ^a	Lebanon	LAP0069	CREA (Italy)	Genetic	4.0	0,0,0	8
				Resource	8		
Ludet ^a	France	Ludet	CREA (Italy)	Cultivar	3.5	0,0,0	7
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645 GP stands for Genomic prediction, QTL stand for quantitative trait locus and n indicates total
646 observations obtained with stem inoculation under controlled conditions. Accession names
647 highlighted in bold were tested in field plots in 2019 and accession names followed by an *
648 were also tested in in 2018. ^a = phenotyped with 1-rows under field conditions in 2019. ^b =

649 presence/absence (1/0) of resistance QTL antr04/05_1 (ALB02), antr04/05_2 (ALB04) and
650 antr05_3 (ALB10). ^c = accession NL01 might have an Ethiopian origin based on plant
651 morphology in the field.
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653 **Table 2.** Pearson correlation coefficients of two high-throughput phenotyping systems, 1) under
 654 controlled conditions and 2) with 1-rows under field conditions, with field plot phenotyping and
 655 genomic prediction values.

Field plot phenotyping, natural infection			Controlled condition phenotyping, stem inoculation			1-row field phenotyping, disease spreader rows ^a	
	2018 n = 7 2019 n = 11	Mean	sAUDPC cc	SDW _{rel}	Lesion _{rel}	sAUDPC _R ow, 1 rep, 1 site ^b	sAUDPC _{Ro} w, 2 reps, 2 sites
sAUDPC _{Field}	F 2018	3.99	0.64	-0.52	0.75*	0.003	-0.19
	F 2019	4.15	0.69*	-0.64*	0.44	0.23	0.48
	M 2018	3.92	0.95***	-0.86*	0.95***	0.19	0.30
	M 2019	5.38	0.77**	-0.68*	0.56*	0.22	0.44
	Average		0.95***	-0.80**	0.89***	0.33	0.31
Yield (dt/ha)	F 2018	42	-0.22	0.19	-0.25	-0.03	-0.26
	F 2019	20	-0.43	0.41	-0.35	-0.18	-0.37
	M 2018	26	-0.79*	0.71*	-0.86*	-0.05	-0.31
	M 2019	14	-0.72*	0.66*	-0.58*	-0.29	-0.54
	Average		-0.64*	0.65*	-0.58*	-0.23	-0.45
Genomic prediction (n=15)			-0.31	0.60*	-0.55*	-0.38	-0.46*

670 M = Mellikon and F = Feldbach, sAUDPC = standardized area under disease progress curve, SDW_{rel}
 671 = shoot dry weight relative to control, Lesion_{rel} = Lesion size relative to total stem length, n =
 672 number of genotypes. * = p≤0.1, * = p≤0.05, ** = p≤0.01 and *** = p≤0.001. ^a = correlations of the
 673 genomic predictions are based on 2 replicates of environment M 2019, ^b = correlations are
 674 comprised of the average of obtained correlation coefficients of all available replications
 675

676 **Figure 1. Disease assessment under controlled conditions and field plots.** A: Representative
677 disease symptoms of white lupin after *C. lupini* stem inoculation under controlled conditions
678 (12 dpi). Disease score index of 1 = healthy, 3 = minor disease symptoms, 5 = average disease
679 symptoms. 7 = severe disease symptoms and 9 = complete plant decay. Plant shown is the
680 reference accession Feodora. B: Illustration of disease foci (brown) occurring in field plots.
681 Disease score index: 1 = no disease symptoms (0%), 3 = minor disease symptoms (>2 to 5%
682 diseased plants), 5 = moderate disease symptoms (>8 to 14% diseased plants), 7 = severe
683 disease symptoms (>22 to 37% diseased plants), 9 = extremely severe disease symptoms (>61%
684 to 100% diseased plants).

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688 **Figure 2. Anthracnose severity under controlled conditions expressed in sAUDPC and its**
689 **correlation with field performance. A:** Estimated means of standardized area under the disease
690 progress curve (sAUDPC) of white lupin accessions phenotyped under controlled conditions (CC).
691 The green dots indicate accessions tested in the field, blue indicates the susceptible reference
692 accession Feodora and red dots indicate the RIL population parental lines, Kiev Mutant and
693 P21714. Dashed line and dotted lines indicate the mean and estimated standard error,
694 respectively, of Feodora. Error bars indicate standard error of the estimated mean. \cdot $p \leq 0.1$, *
695 $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$ and *** $p \leq 0.001$ difference with Feodora (Dunnett's test). **B & C:** Correlation
696 plots of CC sAUDPC and field sAUDPC of each of the four different environments Feldbach (F)
697 2018 and 2019 and Mellikon (M) 2018 and 2019 individually (B) and combined (C). R indicates
698 Pearson correlation coefficient.

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702 **Supplementary**

703 **Table S1.** Pearson correlation coefficients of sAUDPC and disease score at single time point with
 704 field plot phenotyping under natural conditions across four environments. • = $p \leq 0.1$, * = $p \leq 0.05$,
 705 ** = $p \leq 0.01$ and *** = $p \leq 0.001$.

	Controlled condition	H ²	sAUDPC, Field	Yield (dt/ha), Field
706	<i>4dpi</i>	0.76	0.48	-0.10
707	<i>8dpi</i>	0.79	0.93***	-0.66*
708	<i>12dpi</i>	0.82	0.96***	-0.67*
	<i>sAUDPC</i>	0.82	0.95***	-0.64*

709 **Figure S1. Anthracnose severity under controlled conditions expressed in Relative SDW and its**
710 **correlation with field performance. A:** Estimated means of relative shoot dry weight (SDW) of
711 white lupin accessions phenotyped under controlled conditions (CC). The green dots indicate
712 accessions tested in the field, blue indicates the susceptible reference accession Feodora and red
713 dots indicate the RIL population parental lines, Kiev Mutant and P21714. Dashed line and dotted
714 lines indicate the mean and estimated standard error, respectively, of Feodora. Error bars
715 indicate standard error of the estimated mean. \cdot $p \leq 0.1$, $*$ $p \leq 0.05$, $**$ $p \leq 0.01$ and $***$ $p \leq 0.001$
716 difference with Feodora (Dunnett's test). **B & C:** Correlation plots of CC sAUDPC and field sAUDPC
717 of each of the four different environments Feldbach (F) 2018 and 2019 and Mellikon (M) 2018
718 and 2019 individually (B) and combined (C). R indicates Pearson correlation coefficient.

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721 **Figure S2. Anthracnose severity under controlled conditions expressed in relative lesion size**
722 **(%) and its correlation with field performance. A:** Estimated means of relative lesion size of white
723 lupin accessions phenotyped under controlled conditions (CC). The green dots indicate
724 accessions tested in the field, blue indicates the susceptible reference accession Feodora and red
725 dots indicate the RIL population parental lines, Kiev Mutant and P21714. Dashed line and dotted
726 lines indicate the mean and estimated standard error, respectively, of Feodora. Error bars
727 indicate standard error of the estimated mean. $\cdot p \leq 0.1$, $* p \leq 0.05$, $** p \leq 0.01$ and $*** p \leq 0.001$
728 difference with Feodora (Dunnett's test). **B & C:** Correlation plots of CC sAUDPC and field sAUDPC
729 of each of the four different environments Feldbach (F) 2018 and 2019 and Mellikon (M) 2018
730 and 2019 individually (B) and combined (C). R indicates Pearson correlation coefficient.

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734 **Figure S3. Virulence of *C. lupini* strain JA01 and IMI 37515 on different white lupin (*L. albus*)**
735 **accessions.** Box plot showing the standardized area under the disease progress curve (sAUDPC)
736 of different white lupin accessions inoculated under controlled conditions with the Swiss *C. lupini*
737 strain JA01 (red) or Australian strain IMI 375715 (blue). No strain effect (F-value₁₋₆=0.22, p=0.64)
738 and no strain x accession interaction effect (F-value₁₋₆=0.23, p=0.96) was observed.

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742 **Figure S4. Anthracnose development and weather data throughout growing season in Mellikon**
743 **and Feldbach in 2018 and 2019.** Mean DSI indicates overall mean of disease score index across
744 all accessions, mean T and mean P indicate mean temperature (°C) and mean precipitation (mm),
745 respectively, from sowing to harvest. Error bars indicate standard error of the mean. B indicates
746 blue precipitation bar plots and R indicate the red temperature line. Source weather data is
747 Agrometeo 2019.

748

749

<i>Accession</i>	<i>Origin</i>	<i>Genbank code</i>	<i>Institution</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>GP</i>	<i>QTL b</i>	<i>n</i>
Mut28^a	-	LUP 6445	IPK (Germany)	Genetic Resource	-	-	10
Cro01^a	Yugoslavia	LUP 237	IPK (Germany)	Genetic Resource	-	-	15
Eth01^a	Ethiopia	LUP 2078	IPK (Germany)	Genetic Resource	-	-	10
Frieda^a	Germany	Frieda	DSV (Germany)	Cultivar	-	-	19
Sulimo^{*a}	France	Sulimo	Jouffrai-Drillaud (France)	Cultivar	-	-	11
Blu-25^{*a}	Chile	Blu-25	Semillas Baer (Chile)	Breeding line	-	-	26
Feodora^{*a}	France	Feodora	Jouffrai-Drillaud (France)	Cultivar	-	-	37
Amiga^{*a}	France	Amiga	Florimond-Desprez (France)	Cultivar	-	-	20
Figaro^{*a}	France	Figaro	Jouffrai-Drillaud (France)	Cultivar	-	-	8
Zulika^{*a}	Czech Republic	Zulika	Oseva s.r.o. (Czech Republic)	Cultivar	-	-	7
Dieta^{*a}	UK	Dieta	Soya UK (UK)	Cultivar	-	-	8
KievMutant	Ukraine	95413	Polish Genebank	Cultivar	-	-	23
P27175	Ethiopia	P27175	DPIRD (Australia)	Landrace	-	-	18
P27174	Ethiopia	P27174	DPIRD (Australia)	Landrace	-	-	15
Alg01	Algeria	La 572	CREA (Italy)	Genetic Resource	-	-	10
Eth02	Ethiopia	LUP 258	IPK (Germany)	Genetic Resource	-	-	11
Eth03	Ethiopia	LUP 2076	IPK (Germany)	Genetic Resource	-	-	6
NL01 ^c	The Netherlands ^c	LUP 2079	IPK (Germany)	Genetic Resource	-	-	10
Egy01	Egypt	503	Vavilov Research Institute (Russia)	Genetic Resource	-	-	6
MuPI	-	LUP 2104	IPK (Germany)	Genetic Resource	-	-	6
EdwBra	The Netherlands	V11-12-6	Louis Bolk Institute (NL)	Breeding line	-	-	6
Bianca	Italy	LUP 238	IPK (Germany)	Cultivar	-	-	6
Andro	Australia	Andromeda	DPIRD (Australia)	Cultivar	-	-	10
Hetman	-	LUP 6449	IPK (Germany)	Cultivar	-	-	12
Spn01	Spain	-	Local market (Spain)	-	-	-	6
Eth04 ^a	Ethiopia	LAP0084	CREA (Italy)	Genetic Resource	2.1 7	1,1,1	7
Isr01 ^a	Israel	LAP0071	CREA (Italy)	Genetic Resource	3.5	1,1,1	7
Egy02 ^a	Egypt	LAP0093	CREA (Italy)	Genetic Resource	3.3 1	1,0,1	7
Can01 ^a	Canaries	LAP0063	CREA (Italy)	Genetic Resource	3.4 6	1,0,1	8

Leb01 ^a	Lebanon	LAP0070	CREA (Italy)	Genetic Resource	3.5 6	1,0,1	8
Ita01 ^a	Italy	LAP0098	CREA (Italy)	Genetic Resource	2.6 9	1,1,0	8
Ita02 ^a	Italy	LAP0101	CREA (Italy)	Genetic Resource	3.5 1	1,0,0	6
Ita03 ^a	Italy	LAP0099	CREA (Italy)	Genetic Resource	3.6 9	1,0,0	6
Ita04 ^a	Italy	LAP0107	CREA (Italy)	Genetic Resource	3.1 7	1,0,0	8
Sud01 ^a	Sudan	LAP0082	CREA (Italy)	Genetic Resource	3.5 7	0,0,1	7
Mor01 ^a	Morocco	LAP0055	CREA (Italy)	Genetic Resource	3.8 6	0,0,1	8
Ares ^a	France	Ares	CREA (Italy)	Cultivar	4.6	0,0,1	7
Ita05 ^a	Italy	LAP0097	CREA (Italy)	Genetic Resource	3.7 9	0,0,0	8
Leb02 ^a	Lebanon	LAP0069	CREA (Italy)	Genetic Resource	4.0 8	0,0,0	8
Ludet ^a	France	Ludet	CREA (Italy)	Cultivar	3.5	0,0,0	7
					9		

GP stands for Genomic prediction, QTL stand for quantitative trait locus and n indicates total observations obtained with stem inoculation under controlled conditions. Accession names highlighted in bold were tested in field plots in 2019 and accession names followed by an * were also tested in in 2018. a = phenotyped with 1-rows under field conditions in 2019. b = presence/absence (1/0) of resistance QTL antr04/05_1 (ALB02), antr04/05_2 (ALB04) and antr05_3 (ALB10). c = accession NL01 might have an Ethiopian origin based on plant morphology in the field.

Field plot phenotyping, natural infection		Controlled condition phenotyping, stem inoculation			1-row field phenotyping, disease spreader rows ^a		
2018 n = 7 2019 n = 11	Mean	sAUDPC cc	SDW _{rel}	Lesion _{rel}	sAUDPC _R ow, 1 rep, 1 site ^b	sAUDPC _{Ro} w, 2 reps, 2 sites	
sAUDPC_{Field}	F 2018	3.99	0.64	-0.52	0.75*	0.003	-0.19
	F 2019	4.15	0.69*	-0.64*	0.44	0.23	0.48
	M 2018	3.92	0.95***	-0.86*	0.95***	0.19	0.30
	M 2019	5.38	0.77**	-0.68*	0.56*	0.22	0.44
	Average		0.95***	-0.80**	0.89***	0.33	0.31
Yield (dt/ha)	F 2018	42	-0.22	0.19	-0.25	-0.03	-0.26
	F 2019	20	-0.43	0.41	-0.35	-0.18	-0.37
	M 2018	26	-0.79*	0.71*	-0.86*	-0.05	-0.31
	M 2019	14	-0.72*	0.66*	-0.58*	-0.29	-0.54
	Average		-0.64*	0.65*	-0.58*	-0.23	-0.45
Genomic prediction (n=15)			-0.31	0.60*	-0.55*	-0.38	-0.46*

M = Mellikon

and F = Feldbach. sAUDPC = standardized area under disease progress curve, SDW_{rel} = shoot dry weight relative to control, Lesion_{rel} = Lesion size relative to total stem length, n = number of genotypes. * = p ≤ 0.1, * = p ≤ 0.05, ** = p ≤ 0.01 and *** = p ≤ 0.001. ^a = correlations of the genomic predictions are based on 2 replicates of environment M 2019, ^b = correlations are comprised of the average of obtained correlation coefficients of all available replications

A: Controlled conditions

Figure 1. Disease assessment under controlled conditions and field plots. A: Representative disease symptoms of white lupin after *C. lupini* stem inoculation under controlled conditions (12 dpi). Disease score index of 1 = healthy, 3 = minor disease symptoms, 5 = average disease symptoms, 7 = severe disease symptoms and 9 = complete plant decay. Plant shown is the reference accession Feodora. B: Illustration of disease foci (brown) occurring in field plots. Disease score index: 1 = no disease symptoms (0%), 3 = minor disease symptoms (>2 to 5% diseased plants), 5 = moderate disease symptoms (>8 to 14% diseased plants), 7 = severe disease symptoms (>22 to 37% diseased plants), 9 = extremely severe disease symptoms (>61% to 100% diseased plants).

281x208mm (150 x 150 DPI)

Figure 2. Anthracnose severity under controlled conditions expressed in sAUDPC and its correlation with field performance. A: Estimated means of standardized area under the disease progress curve (sAUDPC) of white lupin accessions phenotyped under controlled conditions (CC). The green dots indicate accessions tested in the field, blue indicates the susceptible reference accession Feodora and red dots indicate the RIL population parental lines, Kiev Mutant and P21714. Dashed line and dotted lines indicate the mean and estimated standard error, respectively, of Feodora. Error bars indicate standard error of the estimated mean. • $p \leq 0.1$, * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$ and *** $p \leq 0.001$ difference with Feodora (Dunnett's test). B & C: Correlation plots of CC sAUDPC and field sAUDPC of each of the four different environments Feldbach (F) 2018 and 2019 and Mellikon (M) 2018 and 2019 individually (B) and combined (C). R indicates Pearson correlation coefficient.

387x347mm (150 x 150 DPI)

Controlled condition	H ²	sAUDPC, Field	Yield (dt/ha), Field
<i>4dpi</i>	0.76	0.48	-0.10
<i>8dpi</i>	0.79	0.93***	-0.66*
<i>12dpi</i>	0.82	0.96***	-0.67*
<i>sAUDPC</i>	0.82	0.95***	-0.64*

Figure S1. Anthracnose severity under controlled conditions expressed in Relative SDW and its correlation with field performance. A: Estimated means of relative shoot dry weight (SDW) of white lupin accessions phenotyped under controlled conditions (CC). The green dots indicate accessions tested in the field, blue indicates the susceptible reference accession Feodora and red dots indicate the RIL population parental lines, Kiev Mutant and P27174. Dashed line and dotted lines indicate the mean and estimated standard error, respectively, of Feodora. Error bars indicate standard error of the estimated mean. • $p \leq 0.1$, * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$ and *** $p \leq 0.001$ difference with Feodora (Dunnnett's test). B & C: Correlation plots of CC sAUDPC and field sAUDPC of each of the four different environments Feldbach (F) 2018 and 2019 and Mellikon (M) 2018 and 2019 individually (B) and combined (C). R indicates Pearson correlation coefficient.

383x344mm (150 x 150 DPI)

Figure S2. Anthracnose severity under controlled conditions expressed in relative lesion size (%) and its correlation with field performance. A: Estimated means of relative lesion size of white lupin accessions phenotyped under controlled conditions (CC). The green dots indicate accessions tested in the field, blue indicates the susceptible reference accession Feodora and red dots indicate the RIL population parental lines, Kiev Mutant and P21714. Dashed line and dotted lines indicate the mean and estimated standard error, respectively, of Feodora. Error bars indicate standard error of the estimated mean. • $p \leq 0.1$, * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$ and *** $p \leq 0.001$ difference with Feodora (Dunnett's test). B & C: Correlation plots of CC sAUDPC and field sAUDPC of each of the four different environments Feldbach (F) 2018 and 2019 and Mellikon (M) 2018 and 2019 individually (B) and combined (C). R indicates Pearson correlation coefficient.

385x345mm (150 x 150 DPI)

Figure S3. Virulence of *C. lupini* strain JA01 and IMI 375715 on different white lupin (*L. albus*) accessions. Box plot showing the standardized area under the disease progress curve (sAUDPC) of different white lupin accessions inoculated under controlled conditions with the Swiss *C. lupini* strain JA01 (red) or Australian strain IMI 375715 (blue). No strain effect ($F\text{-value}_{1-6}=0.22$, $p=0.64$) and no strain \times accession interaction effect ($F\text{-value}_{1-6}=0.23$, $p=0.96$) was observed.

177x119mm (150 x 150 DPI)

Figure S4. Anthracnose development and weather data throughout growing season in Mellikon and Feldbach in 2018 and 2019. Mean DSI indicates overall mean of disease score index across all accessions, mean T and mean P indicate mean temperature (°C) and mean precipitation (mm), respectively, from sowing to harvest. Error bars indicate standard error of the mean. B indicates blue precipitation bar plots and R indicate the red temperature line. Source weather data is Agrometeo 2019.

225x204mm (150 x 150 DPI)